

Tutorial guide for SPAP (Database of Source Profiles of Air Pollution)

Step1: Register

Access the site by typing the address “http://www.nkspap.com:9091/” through Google Chrome, Microsoft Edge, or other available web browser.

We also provide open test accounts here for use, and you are welcome to register and use them. (Account: NKUtest; Password: NKUtest2023)

Step 2: Log in

The image shows two screenshots of the SPAP website. The top screenshot is the login page, featuring the Nanhai University logo and the State Environment Protection Key Laboratory of Urban Particulate Air Pollution Prevention. The main heading is '大气污染源谱数据库' (Database of Source Profiles of Air Pollution (SPAP)). A user login form is present with fields for '用户名' (Username) containing 'NKUJZW', a password field, and a 'Log in' button. Below the form is a 'Remember password' checkbox and a '注册' (Register) link. The bottom screenshot shows the dashboard interface. It includes a navigation menu with '首页' (Home page), '数据分析' (Data analysis), '数据管理' (Data management), '用户管理' (User management), and '关于我们' (About us). A map of China is displayed, with various provinces labeled. A table on the right shows data for different particle types and their counts. A red arrow points to a text box in the 'Data analysis' section, which contains instructions on how to obtain source profile data.

2023/3/29 星期三

大气污染源谱数据库

Home page Data analysis SPAP Data management User management About us

更多环境数据

新疆 青海 宁夏 山西 山东 河南 湖北 湖南 江西 浙江 福建 贵州 云南 广西 四川 贵州 湖南 江西 浙江 福建

黑龙江 内蒙古 吉林 辽宁

类型	可用数据	数量	
PM ₁₀	3034	3034	
PM _{2.5}	2518	2518	
PM ₁	60	60	
PM _{0.1}	50	50	
TSP	372	372	
Single particle	单颗粒径谱	794	794
Sum	总计	6828	6828
City	城市	48	48

The recommended source profile data in the data analysis module is used for free. To obtain more source profile, the user needs to send a special application to the administrator or upload the source profile data not covered in the database. After verification, the active source profile in the database can be obtained.

数据分析模块推荐源谱数据免费使用。要获得更多源谱数据，需用户向管理员发送特殊申请或上传数据库中未涵盖的源谱数据，经审核有效后可以获得源谱币，用源谱币可以选择购买数据库里已有源谱。

Apply Upload

发送申请 上传源谱

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Step 3: View, download recommend source profile

Click the Data analysis window. Then click the [Data query] or [Recommend source profile] module.

The image shows the 'Data analysis' window in the SPAP dashboard. The 'Data query' module is highlighted with a red box. The interface includes filters for '粒径' (Size), '城市' (City), '一级源类' (Category_level-1), '二级源类' (Level-2), and '三级源类' (Level-3). A table displays data entries with columns for 'Select all', 'Level', 'Sample code', 'Profile code', 'Sample time', 'City', 'Category_level-1', 'Level-3', 'Sampling position', and 'Sampling location'. A red arrow points to the 'Data query' button.

2023/4/6 星期四

Data analysis 数据分析

大气污染源谱数据库

Data management User management Query 关于我们

推荐源谱数据

Data query

数据查询

粒径 城市 一级源类 二级源类 三级源类 2017-01-06 至 2023-04-06

Size City Category_level-1 Level-2 Level-3

Select all Level Sample code Profile code Sample time City Category_level-1 Level-3 Sampling position

全部 等级 样点编号 成分编号 采样时间 城市 一级源类 二级源类 三级源类 采样位置 采样点编号 采样点名称

		JTJOORMOO2017030901	JTJOORMOO201703090101	2017/3/9	天津	固定源	燃煤源	热力	烟囱	燃煤热力
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Besides that, this page also contains statistical analysis and similarity analysis function which can draw column, column deviation or stacked area charts.

Reference